

Assessment of the Knowledge of Mothers of under Five Children Regarding Worm Infestations

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: A descriptive study was conducted to assess the knowledge score of mothers of under five children regarding worm infestations. **Material and Methods:** The sample of this comprised of 50 mothers. Convenient sampling technique is used to draw the samples for this study. Collected data were analyzed by using description and inferential statistics. **Results:** The mothers mean value for the mode of transmission is 0.29 with the mean percentage of 29%. The mean value of the clinical features of worm infestations is 0.36 with the mean percentage of 36%. The mean value of the management is 0.35 with the mean percentage of 35%. The analysis revealed that there is significant association between age, education, occupation and religion and remaining variable were found to be non significant. **Conclusion:** The study revealed that women residing in community area have adequate knowledge regarding worm infestations.

KEYWORDS: Knowledge; Under five mothers; Worm infestations

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INTRODUCTION

Worm infestation is one of the main cause of childhood malnutrition, anemia stunted physical and mental growth and psychological conditions. It also causes recurrent gastrointestinal and upper respiratory tract infection contributing to high morbidity and mortality in children. Systemic infections are more prevalent among school children aged 5-14 years. Worm infestations remain one of the main problems of child development this is specially a greater health hazard in developing countries. The prevalence of helminthic infestations in an index of the level of sanitation in the community prevention of water, food and arthropod borne.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

A non experimental research design was applied. The setting of the study was Jeolikote area Nainital. The criteria for

selecting study settings are availability of subjects and feasibility of conducting study. The sample of the present study comprised of 50 mothers of under five children. Convenient sampling is a type of non probability sampling was found appropriate for the study. The various steps or strategies used for gathering analyzing data in a research investigation are known as the method of data collection. The investigator had collected the data after getting formal permission from the authority from PHC, Jeolikote and approval was obtained to conduct the study. The participants were informed about the purpose of study and written consent was taken from the participants. Pretest was conducted by administering knowledge questionnaire. On an average each participants took 30 minutes to complete the questionnaire. The investigator did not face any significant problem and the tool was found reliable.

RESULTS

Section I: mean % and standard deviation of worm infestations:

Section II: Over all mean, mean % and standard deviation score on worm infestations.

DISCUSSION

Explore the association of knowledge score of the mother regarding worm infestation with selected demographic variable among mother. Analysis revealed that there is a significant association between Age, Education, occupation, and religion, rest of the variable are found to be non significant.

CONCLUSION

The present study assessed the mothers had inadequate knowledge related to worm infestations. Since increased awareness early diagnosis will be the effective to save the life of the children. Nursing professionals together with their counter parts must organize awareness and screening programmes among vulnerable groups of women’s of under five mother regarding worm infestations.

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